

GO INNOVATIVE: HOW TO IMPLEMENT CROSSOVER LEARNING CONCEPT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract

This article discusses the effectiveness of using crossover learning concept in teaching and learning process. It highlights the positive impact of merging informal and formal learning environments and how it results in the improvement of students' skills and knowledge during study.

Key words

Crossover learning, informal and formal learning settings, teaching and learning, development of skills.

“A good teacher can inspire hope, ignite the imagination and instill a love of learning”

Brad Henry (American Politician)

The role of a teacher requires a lot: from sharing the knowledge to being a mentor, advisor and a model for students.

As a teacher who cares about the engagement of students and the teaching and learning environment, we should always refresh the learning process in our classroom. In the era of globalization and technical advancement, it is possible to move from traditional learning settings to informal learning environment. This can be achieved through

Crossover learning concept that is well applicable for language teaching classes. Being one of the ten innovations in Modern Pedagogy, it combines the strength of both formal and informal environment, and allows students to benefit from the crossover between them (Sharples et al., 2015). The main idea of the concept is to bring the students from “seat-time” classroom learning to the outside school learning which supports students to develop necessary skills and implement the knowledge gained in the classroom in a real environment. A common example of crossover learning process is the Museum visits, library sessions, Sports clubs and others with the main purpose of strengthening educational aspects. The implementation of the crossover learning concept in teaching and learning can be beneficial in followings:

- Learning in the classroom can be enriched by experiences from everyday life;
- Informal learning can be deepened by adding questions and knowledge from the classroom;
- Connected experiences increase interest and motivation to learn;(Panke, 2017)

How did the concept work in my classroom?

I teach Basics of English for Academic Purposes and use “Gateway B1” by David Spencer. Having been interested in the effectiveness of the concept I designed a session in the University Library for the unit “Read on” which deals with fiction and non-fiction types of books and different genres and provides wide range of topic related vocabulary. It took me some time to arrange a session, since it did not depend only on me; I worked in collaboration with the library staff to organize the event. So, if you decide to hold a session outside the classroom, you should allocate some extra time for the organizational issues. The lesson combined both group work and individual work activities, where students were divided into

groups and asked to find as many as possible fiction and non-fiction books and provide the information on books paying attention to the book cover and other details. This part of the session was rather dynamic and students were actively engaged in the process, since the sense of competition encouraged them to work effectively in the group. The second part of the session was based on “click onto” section of the book, where students learnt what the prologue was, discussed the exercises in the book and using the information from this section were required to find the prologues from the books and identify the main idea of the selected books. Overall, the feedback collected from the students proved the session to be successful, as they highlighted dynamic activities and a lot of fun during the session. Moreover, students mentioned that they had started differentiating the types and genres of the books and using obtained knowledge while buying books.

From a teacher’s perspectives I have found out 100% engagement of my students, since the concept encourages student-centered approach giving the opportunity to gain authentic experience; However, the main limitations of the crossover learning process are the difficulties in the organizational process and time management during the session, as students are actively engaged and enjoy the process being in the informal process.

In conclusion, if you want to achieve the involvement of your students in an authentic environment and help them to develop necessary skills, then I recommend using crossover learning process in your teaching. However, the preparation for the session should start 2-3 days prior to the session in order to bring more effectiveness.

References:

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